

**ATROCITIES AGAINST SCHEDULED TRIBE AND SCHEDULED CASTE
AND REDRESSAL OF HUMAN RIGHT VIOLATION**

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Abstract:

Social stratification promotes social mobility and expedites the casteism. Root cause for atrocities among the weaker section of the society is by the dominant caste society. The Indian constitutional Mechanism provides safeguards for weaker and under privileged section of the society. Financial inclusion should provide. Minorities may act as a bridge between developing India and Developed India, so utmost care is taken for the upliftment of weaker section of the society

Key words: *social stratification, financial inclusion*

Introduction

Indian constitution put forth the notion of unity in diversity. Every society shows remarkable feature of its stratification in higher or lower or superior or inferior in relation to each other. “unstratified society with real equality, is a myth that has never been realized in the history of mankind”- (P.A.Sorokin).social stratification may regarded as the classification of people as per their social role in the society. Thus the process of stratification people are fixed in the social structure of the society

Stratification assumes three main forms

caste

estates

class

Showing stratification of Indian society

Social stratification promotes social mobility but on huge cost. Remarkable feature of Indian Society is social stratification. Stratification of society marginalized and exploited the people.

Indians society stratification is based upon the notion of division of labor which provides equal opportunity to each and everyone. The main concern of is to sabotage the vertical inequality into horizontal equality. Providing equal opportunity and freedom of choice. Government of India provides safeguards to schedule caste so called ‘dalits’ and schedule tribes so called ‘adivasi’ in the shape of age relaxation, opportunity in government jobs, free ration even commission has been set for welfare and to provides safeguards to ST & SC (National Commission For Schedule Caste & National Commission For Schedule Tribe) providing post – metric scholarship to students for higher education etc.

As per 2011 census population of Schedule caste in India is 166635700 and population of Schedule Tribe is 84326240 that was 16.66 % and 8.6 % respectively which although equal to the population of United Kingdom vendetta is that still cases has being registered in India about atrocities against scheduled tribe and scheduled caste. Census recorded that dalits population shows decadal growth of 20.8% where as Indian population grows at 17.7 % during the same period. So rigorous step should be taken up for the upliftment of so called Dalits and Adivasi

Subject	Indian	Universal
Declaration Of Rights	Constitution	Human Rights
Equality before law	Art 14	Art 7
Prohibition of discrimination on grounds of religion Race, caste, sex, place or birth	Art 15	Art (Para 1)
Protection of life and liberty	Art 21	Art 3
Right of constitutional remedies	Art 32 (1)	Art 8

- In addition provisions as per Indian Constitution some special provision are made for the deprived classes of the society. Article 17 abolished to practice of untouchability. Article 330 and 332 reservation of seats in appointments. Article 338 made provision for the special officer to investigate the matters related to the safeguards for the schedule caste.
- Human rights Act 1993: says the set up of a National Human rights Commission, State Human rights Commission and Human rights courts for protection, welfare of rights of individual.

- Scheduled Tribe and Scheduled Caste (Prevention of Atrocities Act 1989): act as tool for registering the cases under and trial under special courts to provide relief and rehabilitation to the victims.

Crimes and problems against Scheduled Tribe and Scheduled Caste

- As per the reports of National Commission women of Scheduled Caste are the victims of rape by upper caste man so called Dabang.
- Dalits were beaten by upper caste who questioned on the wages provided to them.
- Scheduled Caste were burnt alive for minimum wages in Belchi village of Kurmi landlords
- Literacy rate among them is very low
- Small percentage of the population participates in occupational activities
- Unemployment among Scheduled Tribe and Scheduled Caste is at threshold and many more.
- District Saharanpur in U.P. faces large number of cases regarding crimes and atrocities among SC/AT. Pertinent to mention here 12 Dalits seriously injured and 55 houses set on fire, ransacked, demolished and looted by the so called dominant "Rajpit"

Conclusion

To promote welfare of Scheduled Tribe and Scheduled Caste financial inclusion is one of the major tools various services like pensions, insurance and loans provided to them for various purposes. Financial Inclusion act as a sine-quo-non for disadvantage and weaker section of the society. Financial Inclusion act as modern machine for realization of goals of weaker section of the society. Survey must be conducted at national and state level classified of Scheduled Tribe and Scheduled Caste as per the needs further welfare programs must be initiative

Minorities may act as a bridge between developing India and Developed India, so utmost care is taken for the upliftment of weaker section of the society.

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